

(12) **United States Patent**
Polyakov et al.

(10) **Patent No.:** **US 11,929,549 B1**
(45) **Date of Patent:** **Mar. 12, 2024**

- (54) **DEPLOYABLE REFLECTOR**
- (71) Applicant: **TRANSFORMABLE STRUCTURES.GEORGIA T.S. GEORGIA LLC**, Tbilisi (GE)
- (72) Inventors: **Maxym Polyakov**, Edinburgh (GB); **Elguja Medzmariashvili**, Tbilisi (GE)
- (73) Assignee: **PIPL LIMITED**, Limassol (CY)
- (*) Notice: Subject to any disclaimer, the term of this patent is extended or adjusted under 35 U.S.C. 154(b) by 0 days.
- (21) Appl. No.: **18/287,002**
- (22) PCT Filed: **Apr. 14, 2022**
- (86) PCT No.: **PCT/GE2022/050002**
§ 371 (c)(1),
(2) Date: **Oct. 14, 2023**
- (87) PCT Pub. No.: **WO2022/219364**
PCT Pub. Date: **Oct. 20, 2022**
- (30) **Foreign Application Priority Data**
Apr. 14, 2021 (GE) AP 2021 15604
- (51) **Int. Cl.**
H01Q 15/16 (2006.01)
H01Q 1/28 (2006.01)
- (52) **U.S. Cl.**
CPC **H01Q 1/288** (2013.01); **H01Q 15/161** (2013.01)
- (58) **Field of Classification Search**
CPC H01Q 1/288; H01Q 15/161
See application file for complete search history.

- (56) **References Cited**
- U.S. PATENT DOCUMENTS
- 5,680,145 A * 10/1997 Thomson H01Q 15/161 343/915
- 5,969,695 A * 10/1999 Bassily H01Q 15/161 343/915
- 2015/0194733 A1 7/2015 Mobrem et al.
- FOREIGN PATENT DOCUMENTS
- GE P20053604 B 8/2005
- GE P20186801 B 1/2018
- WO 2013135298 A1 9/2013
- * cited by examiner

Primary Examiner — Daniel Munoz
(74) *Attorney, Agent, or Firm* — Georgiy L. Khayet

(57) **ABSTRACT**

Provided is a deployable reflector that includes a reflector, a tensioning frame with a deploying ring including upper booms and lower booms, sections composed of lower rods and upper rods and including pantograph levers, stanchions mounted between the upper booms and the lower booms, scissors-like levers located at an intersection of the pantograph levers, first sleeves put on the pantograph levers, second sleeves disposed on the lower rods and the upper rods, cylindrical joints disposed on the second sleeves, an expansion ring for connecting the upper rods and the lower rods, a reflector fixing mesh having triangular cells composed of elastic rods, an upper concave mesh and a lower convex mesh fastened with peripheral units and composed of triangular shape cells, where the reflector is attached to the upper concave mesh directly or is fastened to the upper concave mesh with a spatial shape gasket.

20 Claims, 34 Drawing Sheets

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

FIG. 7

FIG. 8

FIG. 9

FIG. 10

FIG. 11

FIG. 12

FIG. 13

FIG. 14

FIG. 15

FIG. 16

FIG. 17

FIG. 18

FIG. 19

FIG. 20

FIG. 21

FIG. 22

FIG. 23

FIG. 24

FIG. 25

FIG. 26

FIG. 27

FIG. 28

FIG. 29

FIG. 30

FIG. 31

FIG. 32

FIG. 33

FIG. 34

FIG. 35

FIG. 36

FIG. 37

FIG. 38

FIG. 39

FIG. 40

FIG. 41

FIG. 42

FIG. 43

FIG. 44

FIG. 45

DEPLOYABLE REFLECTOR

This application is a 371 national phase entry of international PCT application No. PCT/GE2022/050002, entitled “DEPLOYABLE REFLECTOR,” filed on Apr. 14, 2022, which claims priority to Georgian application No. AP 2021 15604, entitled “DEPLOYABLE REFLECTOR,” filed on Apr. 14, 2021. The aforementioned applications are incorporated herein by reference in their entirety for all purposes.

The invention relates to radio engineering field, specifically deployable space reflectors, and it can be used for large size space antennas.

A mechanical support frame of a space reflector is known (see patent GE 6801, class H01Q 15/16, Oct. 1, 2018) that comprises a mechanical support ring of the space reflector; rings composed of V-shaped foldable rods placed in parallel at the reflector working and rear sides; stanchions between these rods; brackets that hingedly connect the ends of the rods to each other and to the stanchions in V-shape manner; a deploying mechanism composed of cables for winding on drums and drums attached to connecting brackets fastened on two stanchions disposed diametrically opposite to rollers mounted by projections on connecting brackets and rods in intermediate points of breaking rods foldable in V-shape manner, that are attached to the drums at one end, led on the intermediate rods of breaking of the V-shaped foldable rods and on rollers mounted on projections of the brackets, and with the other end is attached to the projections of the brackets by means of tensioning springs; besides, helical twisting springs are mounted on the intermediate axes of breaking the V-shaped foldable rods placed in parallel at the working and rear sides, with arms fastened from the inside of these rods; the brackets that hingedly connect the ends of the V-foldable rods to each other and to the stanchions are made with the arms joined at angles to each other and have H-shape diagonal grooves made from the side of the stanchions, and symmetrical grooves are made in the walls next to the H-shape diagonal grooves and transverse cylindrical axes are inserted; besides, fixtures are mounted on the stanchions to turn the stanchions about the transverse cylindrical axes, and flexible vibration compensators are installed between the brackets of the V-foldable rods of the support ring and the stanchion ends, that are made in the form of cylindrical springs of twisting, which are attached to the brackets at one end, and at the ends of the stanchions at other ends.

The disadvantage of the space reflector is that the deployable ring has low deployment reliability due to the oscillation of the rods when stretching the flexible stretching straps designed for connecting the foldable rods that are hingedly interconnected, and also it is impossible to maintain the accuracy of the geometric shape of the deploying ring.

A deployable space reflector is known (see patent GE 3604, class H 01 Q 15/20, 25, Aug. 2005), comprising a tensioning frame with developable elements forming an approximate surface of the reflector, with an elastic reflector attached thereto; tensioning frame of the deploying ring consisting of hingedly interconnected rods and connected to the peripheral ends of the reflector tensioning frame, and the deploying ring is provided with an opening mechanism with a drive; besides, at the peripheral ends of the developable elements of the reflector tensioning frame, diagonal rods are attached parallel to each other or inclined with the end bended towards the periphery from the elastic reflector fastening side, and on these diagonal rods, a deployable dome frame is connected by fixed or movable connections from the outside of the tensioning frame, with the elastic

reflector mounted thereon such that is capable of merging with the reflector tensioning frame to assume the reflector with symmetrical, asymmetrical, or offset, circular in plan, oval, or polygonal configuration; the stems of the deploying ring are of equal length and are hingedly connected in pairs with each other, and the junction of these rods is located in the middle of the length of the rods or offset from the middle, with the ends of the rods of adjacent pairs of rings being connected to each other hingedly, and to the diagonal rods of the reflector tensioning frame—fixedly or with the capability of sliding, the flexible reflector is made of a whole tensionable elastic mesh, membrane, or of the later composed of individual parts, and the developable elements of the reflector tensioning frame are elastic sheets or flat ribs made of membranes; and the diagonal rods attached to their ends are rigid rods of equal or different lengths; besides, the flat ribs of the reflector tensioning frame are connected to each other with radial, radial-ring, parallel, triangular, rectangular or hexagonal pattern in a plan, and intermediate ribs of rigidity are mounted on the flat ribs of the reflector tensioning frame or on the line of intersection of these ribs; and the connections of the reflector frame and the support frame are stanchions and/or braces; besides, the ends of the braces are connected to the ends of the stanchions and/or each other, while the end stanchion or the end brace is connected to the diagonal rod; besides, the elements of the reflector frame, the elements of the support frame and their connections are located in one or different planes and form a radial, radial-ring or radial-lattice parallel, rectangular, triangular or hexagonal structure in the plan, or a composite structure composed of these structures; and the connections of the ends of the rigid rods adjacent to the deploying ring to the rod of the immovably attached surface forming tensioning frame are cylindrical joints; being movably connected to cardan joints comprising cylindrical joints, and cylindrical units of diagonally arranged vertices of joint rectangles are attached to whole or telescopic rods; besides, the deploying ring is provided with a fixing mechanism, which is a ratchet mechanism, and is arranged on single or telescopic rods attached to a cylindrical unit; and limiters are placed between the ends of the pairs of connecting rods of the deploying ring connected to the diagonal rods with the capability of moving, to limit the movement of these ends; besides, springs for damping the ends of the rods are put on them; and the opening mechanism with a drive of the deploying ring drive is a load-bearing cable, with one end with a spring compensator attached to the end of one of the rods of the deployable ring that are hingedly connected to each other, led along this rod on bearings mounted diagonally on the ends of the rods, and the other end is attached to the drum attached to the deploying ring to wind the load-bearing cable that is connected to the drive.

The disadvantage of the known space reflector antenna is that the deployable ring has low deployment reliability due to the oscillation of the rods when stretching the flexible stretching straps designed for connecting the folding rods that are hingedly interconnected, and also it is impossible to maintain the accuracy of the geometric shape of the deploying ring.

A light weight reflector antenna is known for concentrating radiation (see U.S. Pat. No. 5,680,145, Class H 01 Q 15/20, 21.10.1977), comprising a deploying ring composed of flexible rods with a reflector attached to it; the deploying ring has a truss having a stanchion-diagonal, in the upper and lower boom joints of which a flexible heavy pre-tensioned center is attached, to which a reflector is attached, and the tensioned center consists of flexible straps, the upper

concave and lower convex meshes formed by intersecting, which with their peripheral units are attached to the units of the upper boom and the lower boom of the deploying ring; the meshed have a triangular cell shape, the sides of the triangle are flexible rods, and their intersection forms units that coincide with the vertices of the triangle, the upper concave mesh has a reflector on the bottom, and the concave mesh, which is placed on the top of the reflector with its units, is also connected by flexible stanchions to the corresponding units of the lower, convex mesh, but it happens so that the flexible stanchion, which extends from the upper mesh unit to the lower mesh unit, is passed through the reflector. In addition, the flexible stanchion is provided with tensioning springs. The construction of the central part in this form is associated with many positive factors, including: the upper and lower meshes, with their stretching, which always exceeds the compressive force generated in the mesh rods by various factors, is a geometrically invariant system; as for the tensile forces in the meshes, they are generated by stretching the ridges of the flexible stanchions, which is carried out by the booms placed on it. The structure of such a stretched and geometrically unchanged center also ensures that the ring achieves the shape of an oval and maintains it.

The disadvantage of the known reflector is the low reliability of the structure and its complexity. Although it has a stable form it is well suited to the calculations. Based on these theoretical calculations and diagrams, a geometric shape is precisely achieved. In real conditions, after the inaccuracy of the design of the technological assumptions and the selection of the center elements only by theoretical calculations, deviations from the design location of the reflector fastening units still occur. In such a case, the structure of the center does not allow the adjustment of inaccuracies found after its manufacture.

Also, it is known a reflective antenna system of a deployable reflector (see U.S. Ser. No. 10/516,216, class H 01Q15/16, H 01Q7/02, 18, Jul. 2019), that comprises a tensioning ring composed of pantographs with its structure, by which the upper and lower units of the pantograph are connected to the upper and lower peripheral units of the flexible central part of the reflector antenna; a reflector antenna reflector is attached to the surface of the central part, the deploying ring composed of a pantograph has upper and lower boom sections consisting of flexible rods; which together with the pantograph form a pre-tensioned cable-rod system, the tensioning forces of the flexible upper and lower booms are selected in such a way that they always exceed the compressive forces that are also generated in them by the reflector center tensioning. In order for the system to maintain geometric invariability, i.e. the upper and lower booms to be constantly stretched, therefore it is necessary that the tensioning forces generated by the pantographs exceed the compressive forces generated by the tensioning of the center of the reflector antenna in the booms; at the same time, the deploying ring is deployed and, as a result, the upper and lower booms are stretched by pulling the load-bearing cable passed through unilaterally inclined pantographs by an electric drive in the direction of each other, and in the last stage of the deployment of the deploying ring with the load-bearing cable, the movement of the upper and lower units towards each other is restricted; with a tube attached to one unit, in which the cable is passed, it is abuted and folded at the second unit. From this point on, the structure of the deploying ring changes and is supplemented by stanchions made of rigid rods.

The disadvantage of the known reflector is the low reliability and complexity of the construction, which is

caused by the over tension of the levers under the influence of the tensioning cable passed in the unilaterally located levers of the pantograph of the deploying ring. Such a picture of the position of the load-bearing cable causes asymmetric tensioning of the ring. Performing flexible joints of the upper and lower booms with one-sided joints, on the one hand, requires them to be stretched so that the tensile force exceeds the compressive force directed towards the center, and on the other hand—to maintain the value of this stretch during the whole operation, which is specifically difficult to achieve, at the last stage of deployment of the ring, a change in the specific structure of the ring, which is manifested by the formation of stanchions therein, leads to an increase in the weight of the construction and the existence of a complex scheme of locking mechanisms, in addition to the above, the use of flexible rods in the booms adversely alters the mechanics of the deploying ring, especially maintaining its stability in the process of oscillations.

The technical result of the invention is improving the reliability of the reflector structure by maintaining the accuracy of the geometric shape of the deploying ring and increasing the synchronicity and maintaining the geometric shape of the reflector, as well as reducing the structure weight and simplifying the structure.

The essence of the invention is that the deployable reflector comprises an elastic reflector **53** composed of elastic rods, a reflector tensioning frame **1**, a reflector tensioning frame **1** with a deploying ring **2** comprising an upper **28** and lower **29** booms composed of hingedly interconnected lower **14** and upper **15** rods; and connected to the peripheral ends of the reflector tensioning frame **1**; the adjacent lower **14** and upper **15** rods of the upper and lower booms are connected to each other by space-oriented units **11** comprising foldable rods connecting consoles **76** to which key sheets **75** are attached, and are connected to the reflector **53** unit **52**, the deploying ring **2** is provided with an opening mechanism with a drive **33**, which is a load-bearing cable **27**, one end of which is fixed to a roller **30** existing at the ends of the foldable rods **14**, **15** of the upper **28** and also the lower **29** booms, and the other end is mounted on an electric drive **33** and is capable of winding on a drum **35** mounted on the drive axis; sections **3** are composed of hingedly interconnected elastic foldable rods **14**, **15** of the deploying ring, each of the sections also comprising crosswise intersecting pantographic levers **5** interconnected by a cylindrical joint **6** (**4**), upper concave **40** and a lower convex meshes **41** that are fastened with their peripheral units in the units **38**, **39** of attachment of the meshes to the upper **28** boom and, respectively, to the lower **29** boom of the deploying ring **2**; flexible stanchions **46**, **47** mounted between the upper **28** and lower **29** booms that are elastic rods; besides, the scissors-like levers **7** are located on the central unit **6** at the intersection of the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers **5**, with sleeves **8** put on the ends of the pantograph levers **5** from another side; also on the ends of the upper and lower boom rods **14.15**, sleeves **16** for putting on are disposed, on which cylindrical joints **17** are disposed; besides, the expansion ring **2** comprises the upper and lower foldable rods connecting means made in the form of an elastic rod **62** that is attached by one end to the axis **61** of the intermediate connecting cylindrical joint **20** of the foldable rods **14**, **15**, and by the other end is fastened on a reel **65** disposed on the rotary axis **64** of the cylindrical joints **4** that connect the intersecting pantographic levers **5**, and is capable of winding thereon, or in the form of a tube **70** the reel has on its wings cutouts **67** for fixing the plates **22** that connect the foldable rods in the folded state, and, also,

between the spatially oriented units **11** which connect the hingedly interconnected adjacent upper and lower boom rods **14,15**, there is provided a distance adjusting telescopic limiters (**100**) which are attached to the spatially oriented units **11**; in addition, it also comprises a reflector fixing mesh **55** with triangular cells composed of elastic rods **54** that is fastened in the units **52** of connection of the reflecting mesh **53** rods, and with **56** units with springs **56** at its end, together with the reflector **53**, is fastened in the units **38** of attachment of meshes to the upper boom, that are attached to the projection **36** of the spatially oriented units **11** of the upper boom, on the shelf **58** located above the units; besides, the upper concave and lower convex meshes **40, 41** are composed of triangular shape cells by the units of connection of the sides of which the upper concave and lower convex meshes **40,41** are connected to the reflective mesh **53**; and on the elastic rods **54** of the reflector fixing mesh **55**, when they are positioned at different levels, additional elastic rods **88** are arranged on the reflector attachment side on the elastic rods **54** to equalize their levels; besides, the stanchions consisting of flexible upper **46** and lower **47** portions mounted between the upper concave mesh and the lower convex mesh are provided with tensioning springs **50** and with spring-length regulating devices mounted inside the springs, that is made in the form of a telescopic limiter **89**; besides, the reflective mesh is attached to the intersection units **43** of the elastic rods of the upper concave mesh **40** directly, or in the upper concave mesh units **43** the lower ends are fastened with a spatial shape gasket **51**, the upper ends of which are attached to the tensioned reflector **53** units **52** and to the reflector fixing mesh disposed above or under it; besides, the spatial shape gasket **51** is capable of changing the length between its lower and upper parts.

The scissor-like levers **7** located at the central unit at the intersection of the pantographic levers **5** with the sleeves put on them are designed to be disposed in the plane of the section **3** of the pantographic levers **5** and symmetrically with respect to the longitudinal symmetry axes.

The load-bearing cables **27** are led separately onto rollers fastened on axes of cylindrical joints of the upper and lower booms oriented units **11** and their one ends are fixed on a roller along the upper and lower booms, while the other ends are fixed in the electric drives.

The electric drives of the deploying mechanism **33** are fastened to one of the rollers of the upper, as well as of the lower boom, and the load-bearing cable winding drums **35** are fastened to the axis of the electric drives.

One end of the flexible stanchions **92** that connect the upper concave mesh and the lower convex mesh is fastened in the units **43** of intersection of the triangular cells that constitute the upper convex mesh **43**, and the other end is passed through a hole **93** made in the intersection unit **41** of the elastic rods of the lower convex mesh **41** and is attached to the unit of intersection of the flexible rods **44** of the lower convex mesh at the **96** end of the length-adjusting screw device **96** located inside the tensioning spring **94** abutted from outside; at the same time, to the hole **93** made in the intersection units **45** adjacently attached is a latch **98, 99** for limiting the motion of the flexible stand **92** tensioning spring **94**.

Flexible stanchions connecting the upper concave mesh and the lower convex mesh are made in two parts **46, 47** and the tensioning springs **50** and the telescopic limiters adjusting the spring length **89** are fixed between them, one end of the stanchions **46, 47** is attached to the intersecting units **43** of constituent triangular cells of the upper concave mesh **40**,

and the other end is attached to the intersecting units of the constituent triangular cells of the lower concave mesh **41**.

Additional flexible rods **88** stacked on the side of the reflector attachment to the elastic rods of the reflector fixing mesh **55** are located between the elastic mesh units and adjacent units.

To change the length between the lower and upper parts of the spatial gasket **51**, additional gaskets **83** are placed to change the length of the spatial gaskets by changing their number.

The spatial shaped gasket **51** for changing the length between its lower and upper parts, screw holes **85** are arranged in its lower and upper parts, between which an axis **87** with thread of different directions is placed.

Flexible stanchions **92** for connecting the upper and lower meshes, which are passed through the hole **93** made at the intersection unit of the elastic rods of the lower convex mesh, are provided with latches **97, 98, 99** adjacent to holes, at both sides, for limiting the motion of the spring.

The telescopic limiter **100** attached to adjust the distance between the oriented units **11** of the upper and lower booms has an threaded adjusting rod **103** located on the inner tube **102** to adjust the length of the telescopic limiter and fix the reflector antenna in the designed state at the end of the process deployment.

A tube **70** that is disposed between the intermediate units **20** of the foldable rods and the central unit **6** of every section **3** of the deploying ring is fastened by means of a fastening means **68** disposed on the rotary axis **64** of the central unit **6** of every section **3** of the deploying ring, other ends of the tubes **70** at both sides reach the intermediate units **19** that connect the foldable rods of the foldable lower and upper booms of the tensioning frame of the deployable reflector antenna; caps **71** with locking means **72** are fastened on the ends of the tubes **70** for limiting the sliding by influence of the load-bearing cable led on the roller disposed at the end of the plates that connect the foldable upper and lower rods of the bearer disposed on the shaft of the cylindrical joint that connects the foldable upper and lower rods when the upper and lower booms are fully opened.

The gear-type synchronizers **13** are fixedly attached at the ends of the foldable upper and lower rods **14, 15**, the teeth **72-2** of which abut to one another in the spatially oriented units **11** that connect the rods and are hingedly fastened in the sheet of the units **75** by rods, which has a console-like projection **76** directed towards the central units of the crosswise intersection of the pantograph levers, at the end of which rollers **77** for passing the load-bearing **27** are disposed, the unit **73** is provided with a bearer **78** that is capable of sliding on the tube **70**, which is rigidly **80** fastened on the shaft of the central cylindrical unit with its medium point, and has caps **81** from the inside of the deploying ring and at the ends, with the bearer retaining mechanism **82** to retain the bearer in the fully opened state of the foldable upper and lower rods.

Two pairs of rollers **104** are fastened at both sides of the other ends of the tubes **70** that are fastened by units at the side of the upper and lower booms on the fastening means **68** disposed on the rotary shaft of the central unit **6** of every section **3** of the deploying ring **2**, and the deploying load-bearing cable **27** is led on the rollers, other ends of the tubes **70** at both sides reach the axis of the roller **105** disposed above the cylindrical unit that connect the foldable lower and foldable upper rods of the tensioning frame of the deployable reflector, wherein the caps **71** with locking means **72** are fastened at the ends of tubes **70** to retain the bearer **71-1** disposed on the shaft of the cylindrical joint that

connects the foldable upper and foldable lower rods when the upper and lower booms are fully opened, which is capable of moving by the influence of the deploying load-bearing cable 27 led on the roller 104 disposed at the end of the tube, passing the roller disposed on the cylindrical joint that connects the foldable upper and lower rods, than returning to the roller 105 disposed on the cylindrical joint and led on the neighbouring section.

The description of the invention is explained in the drawings, wherein:

FIG. 1 shows a tensioning frame of the reflector with meshes, in a deployed state;

FIG. 2 shows a deploying ring in a deployed state with an electric drive mounted on a pantograph lever and a load-bearing cable winding drum;

FIG. 3 shows the inside view of an individual section of the deploying ring;

FIG. 4 shows the external view of an individual section of the deploying ring;

FIG. 5 shows the central cylindrical unit of the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers of the deploying ring, external view;

FIG. 6 shows the central cylindrical joint of the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers of the deploying ring, internal view;

FIG. 7 shows the central cylindrical joint of the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers of the deploying ring, the front view;

FIG. 8 shows the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers connected by cylindrical joints with the units oriented in the space of the upper and lower booms of the deploying ring;

FIG. 9 shows the space-oriented units that ensure the oval shape of the deploying ring in the plan, overview;

FIG. 10 shows the gear-type synchronizers arranged on the oriented units of the upper and lower booms of the deploying ring;

FIG. 11 shows a unit for connecting the folding rods with an integrating plate and rollers, whereon a load-bearing cable is led;

FIG. 12 shows the layout diagram of the load-bearing cable of the deploying ring and electric drives;

FIG. 13 shows the layout diagram of the load-bearing cable and electric drives in an individual section of the deploying ring;

FIG. 14 shows the upper concave mesh and the lower convex mesh in the shape of a reflector triangular cells;

FIG. 15 shows a reflector fixing mesh attached to the periphery of the upper boom of the deploying ring with units having springs, together with the reflector;

FIG. 16 shows the sequence of the positions of the reflective mesh (reflective mesh above the fixing mesh), the mesh of the reflector, the spatial-shape gaskets, the upper concave mesh, the flexible stanchions tensioned by springs in their upper parts, the deploying ring and the lower concave mesh;

FIG. 17 shows the sequence of the positions of the reflective mesh (reflective mesh above the fixing mesh), the spatial-shape gaskets, the upper concave mesh, the flexible stanchions tensioned by springs in their upper parts, the deploying ring and the lower concave mesh;

FIG. 18 shows an elastic rod attached to a cylindrical joint shaft that connect the foldable rods;

FIG. 19 shows a cylindrical joint of the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers of a deploying ring, on which with an elastic rod attached to a cylindrical joint shaft connecting the foldable rods to the shaft is fastened and wound;

FIG. 20 shows a deployable reflector in a folded state;

FIG. 21 shows a deployable reflector (embodiment II);

FIG. 22 shows a deploying ring (embodiment II) with an elastic rod inserted in the center of the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers;

FIG. 23 shows the internal view of an individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment II);

FIG. 24 shows the external view of an individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment II);

FIG. 25 shows an individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment II);
in a semi-folded state, external view;

FIG. 26 shows an individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment II);

in a semi-folded state, internal view;

FIG. 27 shows a deployable reflector (embodiment III) with a rod inserted in the center of the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers of the deploying ring;

FIG. 28 shows the internal and external views of an individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment III);

FIG. 29 shows a unit of the foldable rods, with synchronization gears fixedly disposed at the ends of the foldable rods, external view;

FIG. 30 shows a unit of foldable rods with a bearer, at the end of which caps with a retainer mechanism are disposed;

FIG. 31 shows a central cylindrical unit;

FIG. 32 shows a spatial shape gasket;

FIG. 33 shows an additional gasket;

FIG. 34 shows the reduction of the length of the spatial gasket by the removal of the additional gasket;

FIG. 35 shows the increase in the length of the spatial gasket by inserting the additional gasket;

FIG. 36 shows the spatial gasket with a shaft with screws of different directions, the rotation of which changes the length of the gasket;

FIG. 37 shows the flexible rods of the reflector fixing mesh located at different levels, with additional flexible rods arranged on the flexible rods to equalize the levels;

FIG. 38 shows a tensioning spring with a telescopic limiter placed between the upper and lower parts of a flexible stanchion attached between the units of the upper concave mesh and the lower convex mesh of the reflector;

FIG. 39 shows a continuous tensioning flexible stanchion, one end of which is fastened to the upper concave mesh unit, and the other end is attached to the edge unit of the tensioning spring, where a tensioning spring length adjusting screw device is arranged;

FIG. 40 shows a continuous tensioning flexible stanchion, which is attached at one end to the upper concave mesh unit, where the reflective mesh is directly attached to the upper concave mesh unit, and the other end is attached to the edge unit of the tensioning spring, where a screw device for adjusting the length of the tensioning spring is arranged;

FIG. 41 shows a telescopic limiter mounted to adjust the distance between the oriented unit of the upper cord of the deploying ring and the oriented unit of the lower cord;

FIG. 42 shows an internal view of an individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment V);

FIG. 43 shows the external view of an individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment V);

FIG. 44 shows the individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment V) in a semi-folded state, external view;

FIG. 45 shows the individual section of the deploying ring (embodiment V) in a semi-folded state, external view, interior view.

The deployable reflector comprises a stretching frame 1 (FIG. 1), a stretching frame deploying ring 2 (FIG. 2) with sections 3 (FIG. 3 and FIG. 4), wherein the crosswise

intersecting pantograph levers **5** provided with cylindrical joints **4** (FIG. 5, FIG. 6, FIG. 7) being disposed in each section. On the central unit **6** at the intersection of the pantograph levers **5**, the scissors-like levers **7** are arranged, which, in addition to the misaligned position of the symmetry axes of the pantograph levers **5**, by the capped sleeves **8** disposed thereon, provide symmetrical placement of the pantograph levers **5** in the plane of the section **3** and with respect to the axes of longitudinal symmetry. The second ends of the pantograph levers **5** (FIG. 7) are provided with capped sleeves **9** of units that are connected by cylindrical joints **10** to the spatially oriented units **11** (FIG. 8) and ensure an oval shape of a deploying ring **2** in the plan (FIG. 9). On the shafts **12** of the cylindrical joints **10** arranged on the deploying ring **2** of the stretching frame **1** (FIG. 10), the gear-type synchronizers **13** are disposed. The deploying ring **2** of the stretching frame **1** consists of hingedly interconnected lower foldable rods **14** and upper foldable rods **15**, at the ends of which (FIG. 11) capped sleeves **16** are placed, and on these sleeves **16**, cylindrical joints **17** are arranged. The second ends of the lower foldable rods **14** and upper foldable rods **15** are also provided with capped sleeves **18** that are connected to each other by cylindrical joints **20** at the connecting units **19** of the lower foldable rods **14** and the upper foldable rods **15**. On the console protrusions **21** of the extension of the capped sleeves **18** located in the connecting units **19**, one ends of plates **22** connecting the lower foldable rods **14** and the lower foldable rods **14** and upper foldable rods **15** are fastened with cylindrical joints **23**, and the other ends of the connecting plates **22** are joined at cylindrical joints **24**, and on the shafts **25** mounted therein, rollers **26** are disposed, on which a load-bearing cable **27** is led. The deploying ring **2** is a sections **3** of the upper **28** and lower **29** booms consisting of flexible lower foldable rods **14** and upper foldable rods **15** connected to each other hingedly, which ensures the oval shape of the deploying ring **2** of the stretching frame **1**. On the rollers **30** disposed on the shafts **12** of the oriented units **11** of the upper **28** and lower **29** booms (FIG. 12), a load-bearing cable **27** is led in such a way that one end **31** of the load-bearing cable **27** is fixed to the roller **30** along the upper **28** and lower **29** booms, and the second end **32** is mounted in an electric drive **33** (FIG. 13) that is mounted on the roller **34** adjacent to the corresponding boom. The winding of the load-bearing cable **27** is carried out on a drum **35** mounted on the axis of the electric drives **33**. On the upper protrusions **36** (FIG. 3) and lower protrusions **37** (FIG. 4) of the spatially oriented units **11** of fastening the upper **28** and lower **29** booms, an upper concave mesh **40** and a lower convex mesh **41** that have triangular cell shape are fastened respectively, by peripheral units **38** for the upper boom **28** fastening (FIGS. 14 and 15) and by peripheral units **39** for fastening the lower boom **29** (FIGS. 16 and 17). Units **43** of intersecting the upper concave mesh **40** rods **42** and, respectively, units **45** of intersecting the lower convex mesh **41** elastic rods **44** are connected to each other by stanchions consisting of tensioned, elastic upper **46** and lower **47** parts. A tensioning spring **50** is fastened by a unit **48** for attaching to the upper part **46** of the stanchion, and by unit **49** for attaching to the lower part **47** of the stanchion. The tensioning spring **50** is fastened in such a manner that a spatial shaped gasket **51** is attached to in the units **43** of the upper flexible mesh **40** with the lower ends, the upper ends of which are attached to a tensioned reflector **53** by means of reflector units **52** and to a mesh **55** for fixing a reflector **53** being formed by elastic rods **54** having triangular cell shape, that is fastened in the reflector units **52** (FIGS. 16 and 17).

The reflector fixing mesh **55** with units **56** provided with springs that are disposed on the periphery together with the reflector **53**, are also attached to the protrusion **36** of the units **11** oriented in the space of the lower boom **29** (FIG. 15) and it is located on the extension of the peripheral units **38** of the upper boom **28**, on the shelf **58** disposed above it in such a way that the size of each gasket **51** from the lower end **59** of the gasket **51** to the upper end **60** of the gasket **51** is variable and/or invariable. To a shaft **61** of the cylindrical joint **20** that connects the lower foldable rods **14** and the upper foldable rods **15** (FIG. 18), an elastic rod **62** is coupled, which is wound on a reel **65** disposed on a rotary axis **6(4)** of the crosswise intersecting cylindrical unit **64** of the pantograph levers **5** by fastening with its second end **63** (FIG. 19), which has cutouts **67** on wings **66** which, in the folded state of the deploying ring **2**, fix the plates **22** that connects the lower foldable rods **14** and upper foldable rods **15** (FIG. 20) (embodiment 1).

By means of a fastening means **68** disposed on the rotary axis **64** of the central unit **6** of each section **3** (FIG. 23) of the deploying ring **2** (FIG. 22) of the tensioning frame **1** (FIG. 21) of the deployable reflector, whereon tubes **70** are fastened by units **69** at the side of the upper **28** and lower **29** booms, the second ends of which reach the cylindrical unit **19** connecting the lower foldable rods **14** and upper foldable rods **15** of the tensioning frame **1** of the deployable reflector antenna at both sides (FIG. 24). Caps **71** with locking means **72** are fit to the ends of the tubes **70**. By means of the caps **71**, bearer **71-1** of the tube disposed on the shaft **61** (FIG. 26) of the cylindrical joint **20** that connects the foldable rods **15** during the full deployment of the upper **28** and lower **29** booms is fixed, that is displaced by influence of the deploying load-bearing cable **27** on the roller **26** disposed at the end of the plates **22** connecting the upper foldable **15** rods (embodiment 2).

On the second ends of the foldable lower rods **14** and upper rods **15** of the tensioning frame **1** (FIG. 27) deploying ring **2** (FIG. 28), synchronising gears **72-2** are fixedly arranged (FIGS. 29 and 30). The synchronizing gears **72-2** about one another in the connecting unit structure **73**, wherein the synchronizing gears **72-2** with appropriate shafts **74** are movably fastened in the nodal structure sheet **75**. The nodal sheet **75** has a console **76** directed towards the central cylindrical units **6** of intersection of the pantographic levers **5** (FIG. 31), and at the ends of which, rollers **77** are disposed whereon load-bearing cables **27** are led. The nodal structure **73** has a bearer **78** that slides on the tube **70**, which, by the means of rigid clip **80** in the central area, is mounted on the rotary axis **64** of the central cylindrical unit **6** from the inside of the deploying ring **2** and has caps **81** disposed at its ends. The caps **81** are provided with the bearer **78** retainer mechanism **82** when they are in the fully deployed state of the upper foldable rods **15** (FIG. 30) (embodiment 3).

The gasket **51** having the spatial shape (FIG. 32) consists of the lower **59** and upper **60** portions and an additional gasket **83** disposed between them, by changing the number of which increase in (FIG. 34) or decrease of (FIG. 35) the length of the gasket **51** occurs. The spatial gasket **51** can be constructed also as a mechanism (FIG. 36), the length of which is variable. In the lower part **59** and the upper part **60** of the spatial gasket **51**, a double-sided screw **87** having different direction screw **86** is disposed between screw sockets **85**, rotation of which causes changing in the length between the lower part **59** and upper part **60** of the spatial gasket **51**.

Additional elastic rods **88** are disposed at the side the units **52** of the elastic mesh **55** for fixing the reflector **53** (FIG. 37)

11

and they are eliminated at the neighbouring units **52** in order to equalize the levels conditioned by the fastening the elastic rods **54** in the units **52** when the elastic rods **54** of the reflector **53** fixing mesh **55** are arranged at different levels.

In the inner space of the spring **50**, located between the upper part **46** of the flexible stanchion and the lower part **47** of the flexible stanchion, there is a telescopic limiter **89** of over-stretching a spring **50**, at the end units **90**, **91** of which the upper end **48** of the spring and the lower end **49** of the spring (FIG. **38**) are attached.

The upper concave mesh **40** having triangular cells is connected with a continuous elastic tensioning stanchion **92** (FIG. **39**). The continuous elastic tensioning stanchion **92** with its one end is fastened in the unit **43** of intersection of the elastic rods **42** of the upper concave mesh **40** having triangular cells, and the other end is passed through the hole **93** made in the unit **45** of intersection of the elastic rods **44** of the lower convex mesh **41**, and it is fastened to the unit **95** adjacent to a spring **94** abuted from outside of the unit **45** of intersection of the elastic rods **44** of the lower convex mesh **41**. On the unit **95** adjacent to the spring **94** a screw device **96** for adjusting the tensioning spring **94** length is disposed in such a way that a latch **97** for limiting the displacement at the side of the tensioning spring **94** of the tensioning flexible stanchion **92** is fastened adjacent to the hole **93** made in the units **45** of intersection of the elastic rods **44** of the convex mesh **41** on the tensioning flexible stanchion **92** (FIG. **39**).

The reflecting mesh **53** is directly attached to the elastic rods **42** of the upper concave mesh **40** having triangular cells, and to the units **43** of their intersection wherein the elastic rod **92** is fastened. The elastic rod **92** is passed through a hole **93** made in the unit **45** of intersection of the elastic rods **44** of the lower convex mesh **41** having triangular cells. The second end of the elastic rod **92** is disposed on units **95** adjacent to the tensioning spring **94** (FIG. **40**), wherein a screw device **96** for adjusting the length of the elastic stanchion **92** is disposed in such a way that when passing through the hole **93** made at the unit **45** of intersection of the elastic rods **44** of the lower convex mesh **41** having triangular cells, it is provided with latches **98** and **99** at both sides of the hole **93** for limiting the further displacement (FIG. **40**).

A telescopic limiter **100** is attached for adjusting the distance between the upper boom **28** oriented unit **11** of the tensioning frame deploying ring **2** and the lower boom **29** oriented unit **11**, the outer tube **101** (FIG. **41**) of which is rigidly mounted in the upper oriented unit **11** and the inner tube **102** is also rigidly mounted in the lower oriented unit **11**, with the capability of being regulated, which is performed by a thread made on an adjusting rod **103** and fixes the reflector antenna in the design position when the deployment process is completed (FIG. **41**).

By the fastening means **68** disposed on the rotary axis **64** of the central unit **6** of each section **3** (FIG. **23**) of the deploying ring **2** (FIG. **22**) of the tensioning frame **1** (FIG. **21**) of the deployable reflector, whereon the tubes **70** are fastened by units **69** at the side of the upper **28** and the lower **29** booms, the other ends of which reach the axis of a roller **105** disposed above the cylindrical unit connecting the lower foldable rods **14** and upper foldable rods **15** of the deployable reflector tensioning frame **1** (FIGS. **42** and **43**), wherein the caps **71** with locking means **72** for putting on the ends of the tubes **70** are fastened, by means of which the tube bearer **71-1** disposed on the shaft of the cylindrical joint **20** connecting the foldable rods when the upper **28** and lower **29** booms are fully deployed, which is displaced through the

12

roller **104** disposed on the cylindrical joint connecting the lower foldable rods **14** and upper foldable rods **15**, led over the roller **105** disposed at the end of the tube **70**, than returned back to the roller **104** and passed to the neighbouring section **3** by the influence of the deploying load-bearing cable **27** (FIGS. **44** and **45**) (embodiment 4).

Transition of the tensioning frame of the deployable reflector from its folding state to the deployed state is performed in the following manner.

Transition of the deploying ring **2** (FIG. **2**) of the tensioning frame **1** (FIG. **1**) of the deployable reflector from its folding transportation state (FIG. **20**) to the designed deployed state is performed by two independent electric drives **33** (FIGS. **12** and **13**) disposed on the pantograph levers **5** intersecting crosswise by the central cylindrical joint **4** (FIGS. **5**, **6**, **7**) of the individual section **3** (FIGS. **3** and **4**) of the deploying ring **2**, after switching on of which the load-bearing cable **27** wound on the drum **35** mounted on the electric drive **33** axis, which is led separately, onto the rollers **30** (FIG. **10**) put on the shafts **12** of the cylindrical joints **10** of the units **11** oriented in the space of the upper boom **28** and lower boom **29**, and onto the roller **26** which is arranged on the shaft **25** in the cylindrical joint **24** of the plates **22** connecting foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods, one end **31** of which is fixed on the roller **30**, and the second end **32** is fastened in the electric drive **33** mounted on the roller **34**, is deployed and influencing on the rollers **26** of the units **19** (FIG. **11**) connecting the load-bearing cable **27**, the tensioning force of the load-bearing cable **27** is transferred to the connecting plates **22**, one ends of which will rotate about the shaft **25** disposed in the cylindrical joint **24**, and the other ends will rotate about the cylindrical joints **23** disposed of the console-like projections **21** of the extension of the sleeves **18** designed for putting on the lower foldable **14** and upper foldable rods. At the same time, the ends of the lower **14** and upper **15** rods with the sleeves **18** intended to be put on, which are rigidly fastened at both sides of the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods, will start rotating about the cylindrical joint **20** disposed in the unit **19** connecting the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods. As a result, the connecting plates **22** and, respectively, the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods will start deploying. Besides, in the process of being deployed, the cylindrical joints **17** arranged on the sleeves **16** intended for putting on the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rod ends that are disposed on the shafts **12** (FIGS. **8** and **10**) of the cylindrical joints **10** of the spatially oriented units **11**, and the gear synchronizers **13** rigidly connected thereto ensure synchronized deployment of the deploying ring **2** of the tensioning frame **1** of the reflector, start rotating. As a result of increase in the distance between the spatially oriented units (the reflector antenna central part fastening units) **11** for fastening the upper boom **28** and lower boom **29** (FIGS. **3**, **4**, **8**, and **10**), the deployment motion is transferred to the pantograph levers **5** and to the central part of the reflector **1** (FIGS. **1**, **14**, **15**, **21**, and **27**), which, together with the cylindrical joints **10** of the sleeves **9** put on the ends, start rotating about the shaft **12** of the oriented units **11**. The cylindrical joint **4** that enables crosswise intersection of the scissors-type levels **7** disposed on the sleeves **8** fastened on the second ends of the pantograph levels **5** start rotating about the shaft **64** existing in the central unit **6** arranged at the point of intersection of the crosswise intersecting pantograph levers **5**. At the same time, the elastic rod **62** is mounted with one end on the shaft **61** (FIG. **18**) of the cylindrical joint **20** connecting the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods, the other end of which, by means of the fastening **63**, is wound on the reel **65**

13

disposed on the rotary axis **64** of the cylindrical joints that intersects crosswise the pantograph levers **5** (FIG. 19). By means of the cutouts **67** existing on the reel **65** wings **66**, in the folding state of the deploying ring **2** (FIG. 20), plates **22** that connect the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods are fixed, which start moving towards the vertical direction when the tensioning frame **1** of the reflector starts deploying, the reel **65**, on which the elastic rods (cables) **62** fastened on the cylindrical joint **20** that connects the foldable rods **15** of the upper boom **28** and the foldable rods **14** of the lower boom **29** are fastened, is released, after which the reel **65** starts rotating and the elastic rods (cables) **62** having designed (fixed) length that are wound thereon are opened and location of the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods of the upper **28** and lower **29** booms are fixed in the designed state when the deploying ring **2** is fully deployed (FIGS. 12 and 13). Accordingly, the deploying ring **2**, which is connected with the spatially oriented units **11** to the peripheral ends of the tensioning frame of the reflector **53**, will assume the designed oval shape (FIG. 9).

Together with the deploying ring **2**, the central part of the tensioning frame of the reflector starts deploying, which is folded in the internal space of the folded deploying ring **2** (FIG. 20). The upper concave **40** and the lower convex **41** meshes that are attached to the deploying ring **2** of the tensioning frame **1** of the reflector, starts moving together with all elements connected thereto. In particular, by means of the tensioning springs **50** fastened in the units **48** of connection with the upper portion and in the units **49** of connection with the lower portion of the flexible stanchions attached in the units **45** of intersection of the elastic rods **44** of the lower convex mesh **41** and in the units **43** of intersection of the elastic rods **42** of the upper concave mesh **40**, in the internal space of which the telescopic limiter **89** against over-stretching the spring **50** is accommodated, in the terminal units **90**, **91** of which the upper **48** and lower **49** ends of the spring **5** is attached (FIG. 38), interconnected by the stanchions consisting of the interconnected upper **46** and lower **47** parts, and by the peripheral units **38**, **39** of fastening the upper **28** and lower **29** booms (FIGS. 14 and 15), the upper concave **40** and the lower convex meshes **41** (FIGS. 16 and 17) having triangular cells that are attached to the upper **36** and lower **37** projections of the spatially oriented units **11** (FIG. 4), also the reflecting mesh **53** and in order to equalize the levels of the rods disposed above or under the mesh **53** and fastened in the reflector units **52** (FIG. 37) additional elastic rods **88**, the reflector fixing mesh **55** consisting of the elastic rods **54**, the spatial shape gaskets **51** fastened by lower ends **59** in the units **43** of the upper concave elastic mesh **40**, the upper end **60** of which is attached to the reflector **53** and to the reflector fixing mesh **55** by means of the reflecting mesh **53** units **52**, which, by means of the units **56** with springs disposed in the periphery, together with the reflector **53**, is attached on the shelf **58** disposed above the peripheral units **38** of the boom **28** located on the projection **36** (FIG. 15) of the units **11** oriented in the space of the upper boom **28**.

When the process of deployment of the deploying ring **2** finishes, the springs **50** disposed between the elastic rods that connect the upper concave **40** and the lower convex **41** meshes, and the springs **56** disposed in the periphery of the reflecting mesh **53** and the reflector fixing mesh **55**, stretch with predetermined forces, the central part of the reflector tensioning frame **1** is tensioned and assumes the designed shape. In case of deviation of the central part of the reflector tensioning frame **1** from the designed shape, the change of the spatial shape gasket **51** (FIG. 32) length is performed by

14

changing the number of additional gaskets **83** (FIGS. 33, 34, 35). In case the gasket **51** is a mechanism (FIG. 36), its length is regulated by rotating the shaft **87** disposed between the screw sockets **85** of the gasket **51** and having a screw **86** of different direction.

Unlike the first embodiment, a continuous tensioning stanchion **92** is possible (FIG. 39), the second end of which is fastened on the unit **95** at the side of a tensioning spring **94** abutted from outside of the unit **45** of intersection of the elastic rods **44** of the lower convex mesh **41**, where the tensioning spring **94** length is regulated by a screw device **96**, and a latch **97** that is attached adjacent to a hole **93** made in the lower convex mesh **41** at the unit **45** of intersection, limits the further movement of the tensioning flexible stanchion **92** towards the tensioning spring **94**.

The third embodiment is also possible, wherein the reflecting mesh **53** is directly fastened on the upper concave mesh **40** (FIG. 40) and, unlike the second embodiment, latches **98** and **99** that limit the further motion of the tensioning stanchion **92** are arranged adjacent to the hole **93** made in the lower convex mesh **41** at the intersecting unit **45**.

In the process of deployment of every section **3** (FIG. 23) of the second embodiment of the deploying ring **2** of the reflector tensioning frame **1**, on the tube **70** fastened by units **69** of the fastening means **68** arranged on the rotary axis **64** of the central unit **6**, at the ends of which (at the cylindrical unit **19** that connects the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods), bearer **71-1** of the tube arranged on the shaft **61** of the cylindrical joint **20** that connects the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods is displaced on the roller **26** disposed at the end of the plates **22** connecting the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods by the influence of the deploying load-bearing cable **27** (see FIG. 18). When the upper **28** and lower **29** booms of the deploying ring **2** is fully opened, the locking means **72** arranged on the caps **71** fix the tube bearer **71-1**.

In the process of deployment of every sections **3** of the third embodiment of the deploying ring **2** of the reflector tensioning frame **1** (FIG. 28), by the influence of the deploying load-bearing cables **27** led on the rollers **77** disposed at the ends **76** of the key sheet **75** directed towards the central cylindrical unit **6** (FIG. 31) of intersection of the pantograph levers **5**, the synchronizing gears **72-2** movably fastened in the key structure **73** sheet **73** by shafts **74**, will be rotated and the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods that are fixedly fastened on the synchronizing gears **72-2** (FIGS. 29 and 30) will start deploying. On the tube **70** fastened on the rotary axis **64** of the central cylindrical unit **6** by means of a rigid fastening means **80**, the bearer **78** moves. When the foldable rods are fully opened, the retaining mechanism **82** of the bearer **78** arranged on the caps **81** disposed at the tube **70** ends will fix the bearer **78** in the designed state.

In the process of deployment of every sections of the fourth embodiment of the deploying ring **2** of the reflector tensioning frame **1** (FIG. 41), the outer **101** and inner **102** tubes of the telescopic limiter **100** attached in order to adjust the distance between the oriented units **11** of the upper **28** and **29** booms, move and, after the full deployment, it is fixed in the designed state by means of the thread made on the adjusting rod **103** disposed on the inner tube **102**.

In the still another fifth embodiment of the invention, by means of the fastening means **68** disposed on the rotary axis **64** of the central unit **6** of every section **3** (FIG. 23) of the deploying ring **2** (FIG. 22) of the tensioning frame **1** (FIG. 21) of the deployable reflector, whereon tubes **70** are fastened by units **69** at the side of the upper **28** and lower **29** booms, other ends of which at both sides reach the axis of

15

the roller **105** disposed above the cylindrical unit that connect the foldable lower **14** and foldable upper **15** rods of the tensioning frame **1** of the deployable reflector (FIGS. **42** and **43**), wherein the caps **71** with locking means **72** are fastened at the ends of tubes **70** to retain the bearer **71-1** disposed on the shaft **61** of the cylindrical joint that connects the foldable lower **14** and foldable upper **15** rods when the upper and lower booms are fully opened, which is capable of moving by the influence of the deploying load-bearing cable **27** led on the roller **104** disposed at the end of the tube **70**, passing the roller **104** disposed on the cylindrical joint that connects the foldable lower **14** and upper **15** rods, than returning to the roller **105** disposed on the cylindrical joint and led on the neighbouring section (FIGS. **44** and **45**).

In the description of the invention, a deployable reflector is provided that is used on spacecrafts as antennas. Due to its structural scheme, the deployable space reflector ensures reliability and simplicity of the reflector deployment, high rigidity, light weight, optimal shape of the transportation package, technical simplicity of the structure manufacturing, high accuracy of the geometrical shape of the reflector of the reflector antenna and repeatidy of the reflector surface shape after the repeated deployment of the structure.

The invention claimed is:

1. A deployable reflector comprising:

a reflector (**53**), the reflector (**53**) being composed of elastic rods;

a tensioning frame (**1**) having a deploying ring (**2**), the deploying ring (**2**) comprising upper booms (**28**) and lower booms (**29**), the upper booms (**28**) and the lower booms (**29**) being composed of lower rods (**14**) and upper rods (**15**) and connected to peripheral ends of the tensioning frame (**1**), the lower rods (**14**) and the upper rods (**15**) being hingedly interconnected, elastic, and foldable;

wherein the lower rods (**14**) and the upper rods (**15**) of the upper booms (**28**) and the lower booms (**29**) are connected to each other by spatially oriented units (**11**), the spatially oriented units (**11**) including foldable rods connecting consoles (**76**) and key sheets (**75**) attached to the foldable rods connecting consoles (**76**), and the lower rods (**14**) and the upper rods (**15**) are connected to a unit (**52**) of the reflector (**53**); and

wherein the deploying ring (**2**) includes an opening mechanism, the opening mechanism having a drive (**33**), the drive (**33**) including a load-bearing cable (**27**), wherein a first end of the load-bearing cable (**27**) is coupled to a roller (**30**) placed at ends of the lower rods (**14**) and the upper rods (**15**) of the upper booms (**28**) and the lower booms (**29**), and a second end of the load-bearing cable (**27**) is mounted on an electric drive (**33**) and is capable of winding on a drum (**35**) mounted on a drive axis;

sections (**3**) composed of the lower rods (**14**) and the upper rods (**15**) of the deploying ring (**2**), each of the sections (**3**) including pantograph levers (**5**), the pantograph levers (**5**) being crosswise intersecting and interconnected by a cylindrical joint (**4**), an upper concave mesh (**40**), and a lower convex mesh (**41**) fastened with peripheral units of the upper concave mesh (**40**) and the lower convex mesh (**41**) in units (**38**, **39**) of attachment of the upper concave mesh (**40**) and the lower convex mesh (**41**) to the upper booms (**28**) and the lower booms (**29**) of the deploying ring (**2**);

16

stanchions (**46**, **47**) mounted between the upper booms (**28**) and the lower booms (**29**), the stanchions (**46**, **47**) being flexible and including the elastic rods;

scissors-like levers (**7**) located on a central unit (**6**) at an intersection of the pantograph levers (**5**), wherein first sleeves (**8**) are put on the pantograph levers (**5**) from other side on ends of the pantograph levers (**5**);

second sleeves (**16**) disposed on ends of the lower rods (**14**) and the upper rods (**15**);

cylindrical joints (**17**) disposed on the second sleeves (**16**);

an expansion ring (**2**) including a connecting means for connecting the upper rods (**15**) and the lower rods (**14**), the connecting means being made in the form of:

an elastic rod (**62**) attached by one end to an axis (**61**) of an intermediate connecting cylindrical joint of the lower rods (**14**) and the upper rods (**15**) and fastened by other end on a reel (**65**) disposed on a rotary axis (**64**) of the cylindrical joints (**5**) that connect the pantograph levers (**5**) and capable of winding thereon; or

a tube (**70**) disposed on wings cutouts (**67**) of the reel (**65**) for fixing plates (**22**) connecting the lower rods (**14**) and the upper rods (**15**) in a folded state; and

a reflector fixing mesh (**55**) having triangular cells composed of the elastic rods (**54**), the reflector fixing mesh (**55**) being fastened in units (**52**) of connection of rods of the reflector (**53**), and having units (**56**) having springs (**56**) at an end of the units (**56**), the reflector fixing mesh (**55**) being fastened together with the reflector (**53**) in the units (**38**) of attachment of the upper concave mesh (**40**) and the lower convex mesh (**41**) to an upper boom of the upper booms (**28**), the units (**38**) being attached to a projection (**36**) of spatially oriented units (**11**) of the upper booms (**28**), on a shelf (**58**) located above the units.

2. The deployable reflector of claim **1**, wherein the upper concave mesh (**40**) and the lower convex mesh (**41**) are composed of triangular shape cells and are connected by the units (**52**) of connection, wherein the upper concave mesh (**40**) and the lower convex mesh (**41**) are connected by sides of the units (**52**) of connection to the reflector (**53**); wherein, when the elastic rods (**54**) of the reflector fixing mesh (**55**) are positioned at different levels, additional elastic rods (**88**) are arranged on a reflector attachment side on the elastic rods (**54**) to equalize levels of the elastic rods (**54**) of the reflector fixing mesh (**55**); wherein the stanchions (**46**, **47**) include flexible upper portions (**46**) and lower portions (**47**) mounted between the upper concave mesh (**40**) and the lower convex mesh (**41**) and are provided with tensioning springs (**50**) and with spring-length regulating devices mounted inside the tensioning springs (**50**) and made in the form of a telescopic limiter (**89**).

3. The deployable reflector of claim **1**, wherein the reflector (**53**) is attached to intersection units (**43**) of the elastic rods of the upper concave mesh (**40**) directly, or lower ends of the reflector (**53**) are fastened in units (**43**) of the upper concave mesh (**40**) with a spatial shape gasket (**51**), and wherein upper ends of the reflector (**53**) are attached to units (**52**) and to the reflector fixing mesh (**55**) disposed above or under the reflector (**53**) when the reflector (**53**) is tensioned; and

wherein the spatial shape gasket (**51**) is capable of changing a length between a lower part and an upper part of the spatial shape gasket (**51**).

4. The deployable reflector of claim **1**, wherein the scissors-like levers (**7**) with the first sleeves (**8**) are designed

for being disposed in a plane of a section (3) of sections (3) of the pantographic levers (5) and symmetrically with respect to axes of symmetry.

5. The deployable reflector of claim 1, wherein a plurality of load-bearing cables (27) are led separately on rollers placed on cylindrical joint axes of the spatially oriented units (11) of the upper booms (28) and the lower booms (29), wherein first ends of the plurality of load-bearing cables (27) are coupled to a roller (30) along the upper booms (28) and the lower booms (29) and second ends of the plurality of load-bearing cables (27) are coupled to electric drives (33).

6. The deployable reflector of claim 5, wherein the electric drives (33) are fastened on one of the rollers of the upper booms (28) and the lower booms (29), and drums (35) for winding the plurality of load-bearing cables (27) are fastened on an axis of the electric drives (33).

7. The deployable reflector of claim 1, further comprising flexible stanchions (92) connecting the upper concave mesh (40) and the lower convex mesh (41), wherein one end of the flexible stanchions (92) is fastened in the units (43) of intersection of the triangular cells included in the upper concave mesh (40), and other end is passed through a hole (93) made in a unit (45) of intersection of elastic rods (44) of the lower convex mesh (41) and fastened on the unit (45) of intersection of the elastic rods (44) of the lower convex mesh (41) at an end of a length adjusting screw device (96) disposed within a tensioning spring (94) abutted from outside, and wherein a latch (98, 99) for limiting the tensioning spring (94) of the flexible stanchions (92) is attached adjacent to the hole (93) made in the unit (45).

8. The deployable reflector of claim 7, wherein the flexible stanchions (92) include latches (97, 98, 99) for limiting movement of a spring arranged adjacent to the hole (93) at both sides; and

wherein the flexible stanchions (92) connecting the upper concave mesh (40) and the lower convex mesh (41) are made as the stanchions (46, 47), the stanchions (46, 47) being double-portion, and the tensioning springs (50) and the telescopic limiters (89) are fastened between the double portions (46, 47).

9. The deployable reflector of claim 8, wherein one ends of the stanchions (46, 47) are fastened in the units (43) of intersection of triangular cells that are included in the upper concave mesh (40), and other ends of the stanchions (46, 47) are fastened in the units (45) of intersection of the triangular cells included in the lower concave mesh (41).

10. The deployable reflector of claim 1, wherein the additional elastic rods (88) are disposed between elastic mesh units and neighboring units.

11. The deployable reflector of claim 1, wherein the reflector (53) is fastened in the units (43) of the upper concave mesh (40), wherein lower ends of the reflector (53) are fastened by the spatial shape gasket (51) and upper end of the reflector (53) are attached to the units (52) when the reflector (53) is tensioned or to the reflector fixing mesh (55) disposed under the reflector (53).

12. The deployable reflector of claim 11, further comprising additional gaskets (83) configured to change a length between lower portions of the spatial shape gasket (51) and upper portions of the spatial shape gasket (51) and change a length of the spatial shape gasket (51) by changing a number of the additional gaskets (83).

13. The deployable reflector of claim 12, further comprising screw sockets (85) arranged in the lower portions of the spatial shape gasket (51) and upper portions of the spatial shape gasket (51) in order to change the length between the lower portions of the spatial shape gasket (51) and upper

portions of the spatial shape gasket (51), wherein an axis (87) having different direction thread is disposed between the screw sockets (85).

14. The deployable reflector of claim 1, further comprising a telescopic limiter (100) attached for regulating a distance between the spatially oriented units (11) of the upper booms (28) and the lower booms (29) by a threaded adjusting rod (103) disposed on an inner tube (102), the telescopic limiter (100) being capable of regulating a length of the telescopic limiter (100) and of being fixed in a designed state after finishing a deployment of an antenna associated with the deployable reflector.

15. The deployable reflector of claim 1, wherein the tube (70) is configured to serve as a connecting means disposed between intermediate units (20) of foldable rods and the central unit (6) of the section (3) of the deploying ring (2) and fastened by a fastening means (68) disposed on the rotary axis 64 of the central unit (6) of the section (3) of the deploying ring (2), wherein other ends of the tube (70) at both sides reach intermediate units (19) connecting the foldable rods of the upper booms (28) and the lower booms (29) of the tensioning frame (1).

16. The deployable reflector of claim 15, further comprising caps (71) having a locking means (72) and fastened on ends of the tube 70 for limiting sliding by influence of the load-bearing cable (27) led on the roller disposed at end of the plates (22) that connect the lower rods (14) and the upper rods (15), the lower rods (14) and the upper rods (15) being associated with a bearer disposed on a shaft of a cylindrical joint connecting the lower rods (14) and the upper rods (15) when the upper booms (28) and the lower booms (29) are fully opened.

17. The deployable reflector of claim 16, further comprising gear type synchronizers (13) fixedly attached at ends of the lower rods (14) and the upper rods (15), wherein teeth (72-2) associated with gear type synchronizers (13) abut to one another in the spatially oriented units (11) connecting the lower rods (14) and the upper rods (15) and hingedly fastened in a sheet of units by rods, the gear type synchronizers (13) being associated with a foldable rods connecting console (76) directed towards central units of a crosswise intersection of the pantograph levers (5), wherein, at the end of the pantograph levers (5), rollers (77) for passing the load-bearing cable (27) are disposed.

18. The deployable reflector of claim 17, further comprising a unit (73) having a bearer (78), the bearer (78) being capable of sliding on the tube (70) rigidly fastened on a shaft of a central cylindrical unit by a medium point, the and bearer (78) having caps (81) from inside of the deploying ring (2) and at ends of the deploying ring (2) and a bearer retaining mechanism (82) to retain the bearer (78) in a fully opened state of the lower rods (14) and the upper rods (15).

19. The deployable reflector of claim 16, further comprising two pairs of rollers (104) fastened at both sides of other ends of the tube (70) fastened by units at a side of the upper booms (28) and the lower booms (29) on a fastening means (68) disposed on the rotary axis 64 of the central unit (6) of the section (3) of the deploying ring (2) when and the deploying load-bearing cable (27) is led on the two pairs of rollers (104), wherein other ends of the tube (70) at both sides of the tube (70) reach an axis of a roller (105) disposed above a cylindrical unit that connect the lower rods (14) and the upper rods (15) of the tensioning frame (1).

20. The deployable reflector of claim 19, wherein the caps (71) are fastened at ends of the tube (70) to retain a bearer (71-1), the bearer (71-1) being disposed on a shaft of a cylindrical joint connecting the lower rods (14) and the

19

upper rods (15) when the upper booms (28) and the lower booms (29) are fully opened; and

wherein the bearer (71-1) is capable of moving by influence of the load-bearing cable (27) led on the roller (104) disposed at an end of the tube (7), passing the roller disposed on the cylindrical joint connecting the lower rods (14) and the upper rods (15), than returning to the roller (105) disposed on the cylindrical joint and led on a neighboring section.

* * * * *

10

20